

Segmentation of Non-small Cell Lung Cancer (NSCLC) Segmentation on CT Images

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ABSTRACT

Segmentation is an important step in medical diagnosis applications which affects the accuracy of the overall system. The goal of this project is to determine the most appropriate Non Small Cell Lung Cancer (NSCLC) segmentation method on CT images in which 5 patient datasets were used archived from <http://michallenges.org/moistRun>. Comparison between 3 segmentation methods was done, namely multilevel thresholding, region growing, and level set. The region of interest (ROI) was manually defined using either free hand or cubic mask. To evaluate the segmentation accuracy, the segmented structures were examined with respect to the ground truth segmentation results according to Jaccard coefficient, Dice coefficient, False Positive Ratio (RFP) and False Negative Ratio (RFN). The results showed that level set segmentation method that used freehand ROI definition achieved the best segmentation performance as compared the other two methods.

Keywords: Segmentation; non small cell lung cancer (NSCLC); multilevel thresholding, level set, region growing

ABSTRAK

Segmentasi merupakan langkah yang penting dalam aplikasi diagnosis perubatan yang memberi kesan terhadap ketepatan sistem keseluruhan. Matlamat projek ini adalah untuk mengenalpasti kaedah segmentasi tumor paru-paru bersel besar (NSCLC) ke atas imej CT menggunakan 10 data pesakit diambil dari <http://michallenges.org/moistRun>. Perbandingan di antara 3 kaedah segmentasi dilaksanakan iaitu kaedah pengembangan pelbagai peringkat (multilevel thresholding), kaedah pembesaran kawasan (region growing), dan kaedah penetapan aras (level set). Kawasan yang diingini (ROI) ditentukan secara manual secara lakaran bebas atau berbentuk kiub. Untuk menilai ketepatan segmentasi, struktur-struktur yang disegmenkan dinilai berbanding segmentasi sah (ground truth) berdasarkan pekali Jaccard (Jaccard coefficient), pekali Dice (Dice coefficient), nisbah positif palsu (RFP) dan nisbah negatif palsu (RFN). Keputusan yang diperoleh menunjukkan bahawa kaedah penetapan aras (level set) dan penentuan ROI secara lakaran bebas mencapai segmentasi yang baik berbanding dua kaedah yang lain.

Kata Kunci: Segmentasi; tumor paru-paru sel besar (NSCLC); pelbagai paras nilai genting, Kawasan pembesaran, penetapan aras

INTRODUCTION

Lung cancer accounts for around 20% of cancer-related deaths globally (Lozano 2012). The most common type of lung cancer is Non small cell lung cancer (NSCLC). Despite having a slower growth rate than small cell lung cancer (SCLC), there have been reported cases of rapid growth of NSCLC that caused deaths within a short period (Ettinger et al. 2015). As such, effort to develop a computer aided diagnosis (CAD) systems for lung cancer is aggressively explored (El-Baz et al. 2013). Due to the increasing amount of medical imaging data and the powerful computing capability, there has been a rise in the automation of the analysis of such data.

Currently, there have been many imaging techniques used to diagnose cancer such as magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and positron emission imaging/computed tomography (PET/CT). A crucial step in the automation of procedures utilizing PET/CT images is the segmentation of tumour or organs of interest. The aim of the project is to compare three segmentation methods and to choose the best method to segment NSCLC tumour in CT images. The project utilized MATLAB and the method has the potential to be integrated in CAD based lung tumour system based on PET/CT images.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

Within an automated or semi-automated CAD system, segmentation is an important step in medical diagnosis applications and the accuracy of the segmentation is highly critical as it affects the accuracy of the overall system. For the application of detection and diagnosis on lung cancer in particular to CT images, segmentation technique is carried out to segment the anatomical organs of the lungs and respiratory system as well as the tumours. Apart from cancer diagnosis, tumour analysis in CT images is also important for radiotherapy planning so that a proper and suitable radiotherapy can be offered. Thus, this project focuses on determining the appropriate technique to segment NSCLC in CT images.

METHODOLOGY

In this work, three segmentation methods which are multilevel thresholding, region growing, and level set are considered and compared with the ground truth obtained from <http://michallenges.org/moistRun>. Comparison is based on the four established volume overlap measures which evaluate the segmentation's accuracy namely; Jaccard coefficient, Dice coefficient, false positive ratio (RFP), and false negative ratio (RFN). Comparison is also done based on the technique to define the region of interest (ROI) which consists of free-hand technique and cubic mask. However, only one method; the level set, which produced the best result is explained in this section.

LEVEL SET SEGMENTATION

- Step 1: Manually select the first and last slices that contain the tumour/nodule of interest by viewing the sagittal view of a patient as in Figure 1 below.
- Step 2: Take the center slice of the tumour and display the axial view. Manually draw the region of interest (ROI) of the tumour by freeform contouring as in Figure 2.
- Step 3: Crop the image that covers the ROI as in Figure 3 to reduce the processing time of the level set segmentation.
- Step 4: Take the previously manually drawn ROI and fit an ellipse onto that ROI as in Figure 4 (2D ellipse fitting).
- Step 5: Create a sphere as in Figure 5 from the 2D ellipse by measuring the major axis of the 2D ellipse while the z radius is the distance between the center slice of the tumour and the first slice. The created 3D sphere behaves as the initial contour to be deformed during the level set segmentation evolution.
- Step 6: Implement level set segmentation by defining the iteration number and the utilised speed function. Figure 6 shows the level set segmentation result (green contour) with respect to the initial contour prior to level set segmentation.

FIGURE 1. Sagittal view of a patient

FIGURE 2. ROI definition

FIGURE 3. Crop a part of the whole image containing the ROI

FIGURE 4. Fit ellipse

FIGURE 5. Sphere creation

FIGURE 6. Level set segmentation results

SEGMENTATION EVALUATION PARAMETER

In order to quantitatively measure the segmentation accuracy, the segmented structures denoted as A were examined with respect to the manual segmentation results, which is denoted as M , by the expert using Jaccard coefficient (Jaccard), Dice coefficient (Dice), false positive ratio (RFP) and false negative dice (RFN). These measures are commonly used to assess the structure segmentation accuracy when the expert segmentation is considered. The Dice and Jaccard coefficients measure the spatial overlap between the automatic (A) and manual (M) segmentation results ranging from 0 (no overlap) and 1 (perfect overlap). RFP calculates the percentage of A voxels that are falsely included in the final segmentation according to M volume while RFN computes the percentage of missing A voxels that should be included in the final segmentation based on M volume. Both small RFP and RFN values, which are ideally 0, indicate good segmentation results (Yang & Grisby 2012). These measures are defined as follows:

$$Jaccard = \frac{A \cap M}{A \cup M} \quad (1)$$

$$Dice = \frac{2(A \cap M)}{(A \cap M) + (A \cup M)} \quad (2)$$

$$RFP = \frac{|A| - |A \cap M|}{|M|} \quad (3)$$

$$RFN = \frac{|M| - |A \cap M|}{|M|} \quad (4)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For this project, the 10 NSCLC patients are classed into two categories which are juxtapleural tumour and well-defined tumour. However, since the results of patients with well-defined did not show much significant differences, only results of patients with juxtapleural tumour will be shown and discussed in this paper. Also in this work, the percentage average of improvement only utilises the Jaccard and Dice coefficients produced. RFP and RFN values are not used in the percentage average of improvement calculation. Table 1 shows the percentage average of improvement for the level set segmentation method as compared to multilevel thresholding and region growing segmentation methods based on Jaccard coefficient while Table 2 shows the percentage average of improvement based on Dice coefficient.

TABLE 1. Improvement of level set (LS) method based on Jaccard coefficient as compared to region growing (RG) and multilevel thresholding (MLT) methods (%RG = percentage of improvement compared to RG, %MLT=percentage of improvement compared to MLT).

Patient ID	RG	MLT	LS	%RG	%MLT
714046	0.73785	0.75317	0.85089	15.32	12.97
714047	0.74952	0.74062	0.82540	10.12	11.45
714056	0.29935	0.52844	0.58596	95.74	10.88
714057	0.69832	0.67383	0.74343	6.46	10.32
714061	0.87147	0.89064	0.91400	4.88	2.62
Average of improvement				26.50	9.65

TABLE 2. Improvement of level set (LS) method based on Dice coefficient as compared to region growing (RG) and multilevel thresholding (MLT) methods. (%RG = percentage of improvement compared to RG, %MLT=percentage of improvement compared to MLT).

Patient ID	RG	MLT	LS	%RG	%MLT
714046	0.84915	0.85921	0.91927	8.25	6.99
714047	0.85683	0.85098	0.90780	5.95	6.68
714056	0.46077	0.69812	0.73856	60.29	5.79
714057	0.80513	0.82236	0.85284	5.93	3.71
714061	0.94216	0.93132	0.95507	1.37	2.55
Average of improvement				16.36	5.14

Based on the results, the segmentation of CT images using the level set method has produced the best Jaccard and Dice coefficients. The level set method is better than region growing method that achieves an average improvement of 26.50% and 16.36% for Jaccard and Dice coefficients respectively. When compared to the multilevel thresholding method, the level set method obtained an improved segmentation results which are 9.65% for Jaccard coefficient and 5.14% for Dice coefficient. As can be seen above, the Jaccard and Dice coefficients produced by all three segmentation methods for Patient 714056 are the worst among the datasets.

CONCLUSION

As a conclusion, comparison of NSCLC segmentation methods is implemented and the obtained results show that by defining the ROI freely and combined with the level set segmentation method, the accuracy of segmentation is improved by 26.50% and 16.36% with respect to Jaccard and Dice coefficients of the region growing segmentation method. In comparison to multilevel thresholding segmentation method, the level set method produces an improvement of 9.65% for Jaccard coefficient and 5.14% for Dice coefficient.

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